

APP ABOUT DEVICE INCIDENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7647946>

Abstract. *The phenomenon of application-device is a topic that is studied in linguistics, but not fully studied yet, full of different opinions and debates.*

Keywords: *application event, application device, structural group, complex syntactic entity, main expression, application element.*

In world linguistics, specific signs of complex syntactic integrity in certain languages, their similarities and differences are being researched on the basis of comparative typological methods. In many educational institutions and research centers around the world, in particular, in schools of Russian and German linguistics, as well as Uzbek linguistics, scientific research on the application device phenomenon is being conducted. This shows that the lexical semantic, syntactic, morphological and linguo-programmatic aspects of natural languages are different from each other in different degrees and it shows that it is important to cross-examine the structure of several languages, and to study the features of the application device phenomenon in German and Uzbek using the latest achievements of linguistics and advanced methods in practice. creates an opportunity for scientific research.

In recent years, in our country, the system of learning foreign languages has been improved, the processes of integrating science and education with practice, the phenomenon of application, its types and coverage level, syntactically and semantically comprehensive, research on the basis of rich linguistic materials, cross-research with the German language, relying on advanced foreign experiences special attention is being paid. Based on the principles of development, the promotion of scientific research and improvement of innovative activity, which is set as a priority direction in the state program of the action strategy for "...stimulation of scientific research and innovation activities, creation of effective mechanisms for the implementation of scientific and innovative achievements" demands to go.

In modern linguistics, the phenomenon of attachment is a widespread and much-studied stylistic phenomenon. As we explore the research findings in this area, we can come across different types of application devices. They increase the form and effectiveness of the expression in the artistic work, ensure that it reaches the reader easily and understandably, and perform various grammatical and stylistic functions in the text. In German linguistics, this case is studied as a stylistic phenomenon. The case of adjunctive device is important in modern German syntax. German scientists G. Starke, U. Hoberk, L. Spiser and others explain the attachment device in the construction of the sentence by such terms as deviation, exclusion, combination, division or expanding the idea. As a result of a review of the scientific literature, it can be concluded that the phenomenon of adjunct is a characteristic of the German language. By an application device we understand a syntactic unit, which consists of two parts: a main expression and an application element. In this case, the additional element is subordinate to the main part both structurally and semantically. It should be noted that the adverbial element has a secondary character, that is, it always stands after the main expression and fills in, defines, explains and expresses in more detail the events that happened in the main expression. Such a meaning implied by the application

element always has an additional character: that is, the first part conveys information, and the second part conveys an additional message. The writer uses the element of attachment to draw the reader's attention to the event being described, and as a result, it increases its impact and reality. Therefore, the stylistic functions of the additional elements that have the characteristic of formation in such a view are extremely important. As a result of studies in the field of linguistics, it is known that application constructions also have the characteristic of complexity. In the process of such complexity, the number of additional elements joining the main expression in the structure of the application construction increases. The structural expansion of applied elements leads to their expansion in terms of meaning. The expansion of the meaning leads to the diversity of the nuances of the meaning. For example, consider an excerpt from Franz Kafka's *Ein Hungerkünstler*:

Das Orchester bekräftigte alles durch einen großen Tisch; man ging auseinander und niemand hatte das Recht, mit dem Gesehenen unzufrieden zu sein. Niemand. Nur der Hungerkünstler. Immer nur er.

The number of application elements here is three, so this example shows that the above fragment is an example of an application device with a complex structure. In recent years, the study of complex structural application devices both from the point of view of structure and from the point of view of semantic relations between the parts of the sentence has increasingly attracted the attention of researchers. However, the richness and diversity of syntax means that the world's languages must express certain meanings, and there are so many different alternatives that the problem of learning complex sentences cannot be considered complete.

Today, the quality and scope of researches related to the linguistic nature of the text is increasing. The text problem is recognized as one of the most urgent issues in world linguistics. The importance of the topic is determined by the fact that the semantic-syntactic relations between the components of the artistic text do not go unnoticed by the researchers. Also, in German linguistics, as in other linguistics, there is still no clear conclusion about the nature and nature of the construction of the application. However, it is not necessary to prove that the importance of the phenomenon of application in the analysis and interpretation of the problems of text linguistics is incomparable.

In the process of oral speech, the meaning of the attachment part often takes the form of a thought that suddenly occurred to the speaker. This idea is added after the usual prepositional phrase, after a specific pause. It should also be said that the additional idea that can be understood from the appended parts does not always appear to the speaker during or after saying the main (leading) parts. Also, it is not some kind of insignificant (not to mention) addendum from the speaker's point of view. You can find a lot of adverbial constructions not only in prose works, but also in poetry, newspapers and magazines, in popular scientific works. Plug-ins have a number of unique features. They are expressed in the form of cohesive complements. The structural expansion of additional elements leads to the expansion of the scope of additional meaning conveyed by them to the main expression or any of its components. Applied elements differ from directly related applied elements in the structure of a complex syntactic whole in that they have their own characteristics. The presence of additional elements at a certain distance from the main expression performs a number of syntactic-semantic and stylistic functions: the architecture of the text is formed; semantic relatedness increases; continues the main idea.

An application device refers to a complex syntactic whole consisting of syntactically and semantically related components. An application device consists of two parts: a main expression and an application element. An adjunct always follows the main expression. In this case, the additional element is subordinate to the main part both structurally and semantically. It should be noted that the auxiliary element has a secondary character, and the event that happened in the main expression fills the event, defines it, and expresses it in more detail. Such a meaning implied by the application element always has an additional character: that is, the first part conveys information, and the second part conveys an additional message. The writer uses the element of attachment in order to draw the reader's attention to the event being described, and as a result, its effectiveness and reality increase. Therefore, the stylistic functions of the additional elements, which have the characteristic of formation in such a view, are extremely important. Such a definition of an application device has a broad meaning, because we understand that an application device is one of the structural types of a complex syntactic entity based on application relations. For this reason, we use this terminological concept widely in the analysis of structural, spiritual and methodological features of additional elements found in artistic works. Application elements are an integral part of application devices or a complex syntactic entity based on application relationships. So any application device consists of two parts. Application devices are created in order to give a unique meaning and expressive-stylistic color to the speech, to assign a great meaning and emotional task to some parts of the expression, to develop and deepen the author's thought, to convey it to the reader at a high level of expressiveness.

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